

PHOTOCHEMICAL REACTIONS WITH SOME INORGANIC COLLOIDS AS ACTIVE AGENTS UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF LIGHT IN VARIOUS STATES OF POLARISATION PART VI. PHOTOCHEMICAL REDUCTION OF VANADIC ACID SOL WITH ETHYL ALCOHOL IN ACID MEDIUM.

By J. C. GHOSH, T. BANERJEE AND S. K. BHATTACHARJEE.

Merck's extra pure ethyl alcohol, sodium meta-vanadate and hydrochloric acid were used in this investigation. The vanadic acid sol was prepared every day immediately before each experiment by adding to a solution of sodium meta-vanadate a little greater than half the equivalent amount of hydrochloric acid when a reddish yellow sol was produced.

Dumanski (*Kolloid Z.*, 1923, 33, 147) postulates that by the addition of hydrochloric acid to salts of ortho-vanadic acid, the following changes occur.

Lange (*Kolloid Z.*, 1932, 59, 168) determined the relative concentrations of true solutions and colloidal solutions of V_2O_5 by optical methods and his results are given below.

Total conc.	Conc. of colloidal sol.	Conc. of true solution.
14.14M	13.53M	0.61M
7.07	6.26	0.81
2.83	1.64	1.19

In our experiments, the total initial concentration was not less than 8.2 m.M. per litre.

The p_n value of the sol was determined electrometrically using quinhydrone electrode which was found to be satisfactory when an accuracy of ± 0.2 in p_n was aimed at.

Spectrophotometric method was applied for the estimation of the reduced vanadic acid sol. Dumanski (*loc. cit.*) found that when V_2O_5 sol is reduced by hydrazine hydrate, the products exist in the colloidal state

and exhibits all the properties of colloidal solutions. For our purpose, a König-Marten spectrophotometer was first calibrated. The absorption due to reduced greenish blue vanadic acid sol was measured by means of the spectrophotometer in the red region ($632 \mu\mu$), where the absorption due to original vanadic acid sol is practically negligible. Different concentrations of the vanadic acid sol and the corresponding spectrophotometer readings (θ_2) after complete reduction of the sol by alcohol on long exposure to sunlight are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Conc. of V_2O_5 sol.	θ_1 .	θ_2 (zero reading of spectrophotometer.)	$\text{Log tan } \theta_2 - \text{log tan } \theta_1$.
$123 \times 10^{-4} M$	79.7	46	0.7398
82.5×10^{-4}	73.3	46	0.4950
55.0×10^{-4}	65.3	46	0.3161
41.0×10^{-4}	59.5	46	0.2158
27.5×10^{-4}	55.0	46	0.1396
20.6×10^{-4}	51.5	46	0.0839

On plotting $\text{log tan } \theta_2 - \text{log tan } \theta_1$ against concentration of vanadic acid sol, a straight line was obtained (Fig. 1) indicating that Beer's law is obeyed in the case. It is interesting to note that for vanadic acid sol itself Beer's law is not obeyed (Lange, *loc. cit.*) due to the fact that with change in dilution, the equilibrium between molecules in true solution and colloidal solution is disturbed. In our case, however, the total concentration remains constant. What changes, however, is the ratio of micelles in the oxidised and the reduced state.

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

From this standard curve (Fig. 1), the concentration of reduced vanadic acid sol at any time after exposure to ultraviolet light was determined by taking the spectrophotometer reading ($\log \tan \theta_2 - \log \tan \theta_1$) corresponding to the absorption in the red region of spectrophotometer.

Dark Reaction.—Vanadic acid sol is not reduced by ethyl alcohol when kept in the dark for a period of 8 hours at 32° .

Determination of the Order of the Reaction.

TABLE II.

Sodium meta-vanadate as $V_2O_5 = 82.5 \times 10^{-4} M$. Alcohol = $10.4 M$. HCl = $0.01 M$. p_H of the sol = 3.92 . Region = $366 \mu\mu$. Temp. = 32° . * $I_{abs} = 4280$.

Time.	Spectro-photometer reading.	V_2O_5 sol $\times 10^4$.	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$ (zero-molecular with respect to V_2O_5 sol) per c.c. per sec.	K (mean).
0 min.	49.5	82.5M		
90	54.5	63.7	3.42	
192	63.0	41.5	3.50	3.40
326	69.5	21.0	3.32	

The reaction is evidently zero-molecular.

TABLE III.

Effect of varying the concentration of alcohol.

$d = 0.5$ cm. $I_{abs} = 4280$. Temp. = 32° . HCl = $0.01 M$. p_H of sol = 3.9 .

V_2O_5 sol $\times 10^4$.	Conc. of alcohol.	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$.	γ .
82.5M	10.4M	3.4	0.130
"	6.95	2.98	0.114
"	3.47	2.43	0.093
"	1.74	1.47	0.061

On plotting $1/K$ against $1/C$ (ethyl alcohol), a straight line is obtained (Fig. 2).

* I_{abs} here and in the following tables indicates the intensity of radiation absorbed in ergs/cm²/sec. and d , the thickness of reaction cell.

TABLE IV.

Effect of varying the concentration of the sol. $d = 0.5 \text{ cm.}$ $I_{\text{abs}} = 4280 \text{ ergs.}$ p_{π} of the sol = 3.92. Temp. = 32°.

Conc. of V_2O_5 sol.	Conc. of alcohol.	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$.	γ .
$120.0 \times 10^{-4} M$	6.95 M	3.22	0.119
82.5×10^{-4}	„	2.98	0.112

In the above cases, the p_{π} value of the sol was kept constant by trial, by adding, where necessary, the requisite quantity of free hydrochloric acid.

The velocity constant, as is evident from Table IV, is independent of the concentration of vanadic acid sol, when the intensity of absorbed radiation is the same

TABLE V.

*Effect of varying the p_{π} of the system.*Temp. = 32°. $I_{\text{abs}} = 4280$. V_2O_5 sol. = $82.5 \times 10^{-4} M$. Alcohol = $10.4 M$

p_{π}	...	5.0	3.92	3.31	3.10
$K_0 \times 10^{10}$	...	4.12	3.40	2.17	1.55

Temperature Coefficient of the Reaction.—The temperature coefficient $\left(\frac{K_{T+10}}{K_T}\right)$ is small, being of the order of 1.1.

Effect of Varying the Intensity of Absorbed Radiation.

TABLE VI.

Temperature of the thermostat = 32°. Conc. of V_2O_5 sol = $82.5 \times 10^{-4} M$
 p_{π} of the sol = 3.92. Conc. of alcohol = $10.4 M$.

I_{abs}	...	4280	3249	2085	1299	654
$K_0 \times 10^{10}$	...	3.40	2.77	1.98	1.48	0.92

The velocity constant is proportional neither to the intensity of absorbed radiation nor to the square root of the intensity.

Quantum Efficiency of the Process.—The quantum yield of the photo-process is much less than unity.

A typical calculation is given below :—

We shall take, for example, the reaction in Table II.

The no. of Einstein ($366\mu\mu$) absorbed per sec. per sq. cm.

$$= \frac{4280 \times 366 \times 10^{-7}}{(6.55 \times 10^{-27}) \times (3 \times 10^{10}) \times (6.1 \times 10^{23})} = 13.07 \times 10^{-10}, \quad d = 0.5 \text{ cm.}$$

No. of g. mol transformed in 1 sec. in a cell (1 cm $\times$ 1 cm $\times$.5 cm.)

$$= K_0 \times .5 = 3.4 \times 10^{-10} \times 0.5 = 1.7 \times 10^{-10}.$$

$$\gamma \text{ (Quantum efficiency)} = \frac{1.7 \times 10^{-10}}{13.07 \times 10^{-10}} = 0.130.$$

Effect of Polarised Light.

TABLE VII.

$$p_n = 5.0$$

Nature of light	$V_2O_5 = 82.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M.}$	Alcohol = 10.4M	$M_5 \times 10^{10}$.
Unpolarised	...	654	0.92
<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised light	...	560	0.90
<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised light	...	560	0.58

We see from Table VII that *l*-circularly polarised light is more efficient than *d*-circularly polarised light.

DISCUSSION.

The reaction has the following characteristics :—

(a) The velocity of reaction with reference to V_2O_5 sol is zero-molecular.

(b) The velocity constant diminishes as the concentration of ethyl alcohol diminishes, the concentration of vanadic acid sol being kept constant. r/K plotted against r/C_{alcohol} gives a straight line.

(c) The velocity constant is almost independent of the concentration of vanadic acid sol, the p_x value being kept constant.

(d) The temperature coefficient of the reaction is almost unity.

(e) The velocity constant is proportional neither to the intensity of radiation nor to the square root of intensity.

(f) The quantum efficiency is much less than unity.

(g) *l*-Circularly polarised light is more effective than *d*-circularly polarised light in bringing about the photoreduction of vanadic acid sol with alcohol.

The peculiar feature of the reaction is that the velocity constant is neither proportional to the intensity of radiation nor to the square root of intensity. This indicates that absorption of a quantum of radiation $366\mu\mu$ may

(1) excite a V_2O_5 molecule fixed on the surface of the sol, which reacts with alcohol or

(2) dissociate a V_2O_5 molecule into $V_2O_4 + O$, the molecule of V_2O_4 and oxygen atom reacting separately with alcohol.

For reaction (1)

$$\frac{dx_1}{dt} = \frac{i}{Nh\nu} \cdot KC_s \quad \dots (i)$$

(C_s = surface concentration of alcohol)

For reaction (2), since the quantum efficiency is very much less than unity, the surface concentrations of oxygen atom and of V_2O_4 molecule are practically determined by the equation

If the rate of the following reactions taking place on the surface of the micelle are approximately the same

the concentration of O atom and V_2O_4 molecule throughout the process are the same, hence

$$[O] = K_3 \sqrt{\frac{I}{Nh\nu}}$$

$$\text{or } [V_2O_4] = K_3 \sqrt{\frac{I}{Nh\nu}}$$

The velocity of reactions (3) is given by

$$\frac{dx_2}{dt} = K_3 \sqrt{\frac{I}{Nh\nu}} \cdot K_2 C_1$$

and the total velocity

$$K_0 = \frac{dx}{dt} = \left[\frac{dx_1}{dt} + \frac{dx_2}{dt} \right] = \left[\frac{I}{Nh\nu} + 2K_3 \sqrt{\frac{I}{Nh\nu}} \right] \cdot K \cdot C_1$$

The rate of oxidation of alcohol also depends on the surface concentration of alcohol. Hence K_0 (the velocity constant of the reactions) will vary as C_1 .

But since C_1 is given by

$$\frac{K_4 C_{\text{alcohol}}}{K_5 + K_6 C_{\text{alcohol}}} \quad (\text{according to Langmuir's hypothesis})$$

$1/K_0$ plotted against $1/C_{\text{alcohol}}$ should be a straight line, which has actually been found.

The relatively lower efficiency of the *d*-circularly polarised light will be discussed elsewhere in this series.

The effect of p_n on the velocity of reaction in this case is opposite to that observed in the case of tungstic acid and molybdic acid sol. The velocity diminishes with decrease of p_n until we reach $p_n = 3$ when the sol becomes unstable. This can be best explained on the basis that there is equilibrium in the solution between the following forms

and so on.

With increase in the concentration of H^+ , the negative charge on the colloid micelle diminishes, and with diminution in the density of charge, particles become larger and larger. Hence the specific surface diminishes which results in a diminution in the velocity of the surface reaction which we have studied.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
DACCA UNIVERSITY, DACCA.

Received July 20, 1936.